

Determination of Carotenoid and Beta-Carotene Content in *Dunaliella* Microalgae Powder

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Abstract

Nowadays, human demand for natural antioxidants is increasing, gradually replacing synthetic antioxidants. *Dunaliella* microalgae is an important source of carotenoid production, with beta-carotene accumulating at high concentrations and having practical applications in nutrition, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. Raw powder from *D. bardawil* and *D. salina* algae cultivated in Vietnam needs to be characterized in terms of morphological features, carotenoid, and beta-carotene content before application in production and commercial use. Morphological characteristics of microalgae powder were evaluated through naked eye observation and optical microscopy. The UV-Vis method was used to assess total carotenoid content in hexane extract. Beta-carotene quantification was performed using HPLC with a gradient method, using a mobile phase of Dichloromethane: Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:45:15). Results showed that *D. bardawil* and *D. salina* powders were homogeneous, with a yellow color and intact cells. Total carotenoid accumulation was high, with *D. bardawil* (3.306 mg/g) significantly higher than *D. salina* (1.454 mg/g) ($p < 0.05$). HPLC conditions for beta-carotene analysis were reliable, with a retention time of 11.942 minutes, tail factor (Tf) < 2 , and theoretical plate number > 3000 . Beta-carotene content was significantly higher in *D. bardawil* (0.172 mg/g) compared to *D. salina* (0.117 mg/g) ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, raw powder from *D. bardawil* and *D. salina* algae are suitable for beta-carotene production for applications in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and commercial products.

Introduction

Dunaliella was first discovered in 1838 by Michael Felix Dunal, and to date, 28 *Dunaliella* species have been recognized [1]. This halophilic green algae is found in natural marine environments, where it can create red-colored water [2]. Two species, *Dunaliella salina* and *Dunaliella salina* var. *bardawil* (*D. bardawil*), have been extensively studied due to their ability to provide large amounts of natural beta-carotene up to 14% of dry algal weight and their adaptability to various conditions [3], [4]. According to Olmos *et al.* (2000), based on 18S rRNA gene sequencing, it is possible to differentiate between the two species *D. salina* and *D. bardawil* [5].

Carotenoids are tetraterpenic compounds found in plants, fungi, algae, and bacteria. Humans cannot synthesize carotenoids and must obtain them externally. Common carotenoids in *Dunaliella* include beta-carotene, lutein, phytoen, zeaxanthin, and other valuable bioactive compounds such as glycerol, carbohydrates, lipids, proteins, vitamins, and minerals [6]. Beta-carotene is the most common and stable natural carotenoid found in nature. It functions as a pro-vitamin A (retinol) and can be converted to vitamin A in the human body, where it exhibits antioxidant properties and demonstrates potential anti-cancer and cardiovascular protective effects [7]. Beta-carotene, astaxanthin, lutein, and lycopene are the primary

More Information

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carotenoids with commercial value found in microalgae, approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for direct human use [8].

The primary sources of beta-carotene are chemical synthesis (84.8%), while beta-carotene extracted from algae accounts for 8.5% and from plants for 6.7% [9]. *Dunaliella* is emerging as an increasingly attractive source of beta-carotene, with promising practical applications in nutrition, pharmaceutical, cosmetic industries, and genetic engineering research [10]. Morowvat and Ghasemi (2016) used reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method to analysis β -carotene content from acetone and chloroform (2:1 v/v) extract of unicellular green microalga *Dunaliella salina*. The method was chromatographed using a C18 chromatography column with methanol: chloroform (85:15 v/v) and 2.0 mL min^{-1} flow rate. The analytical method might be magnificently exploited for β -carotene quantification in *D. salina* and also other related microalgal strains [11]. *Dunaliella salina* cultivated with bicarbonate as carbon source and under optimized condition, a maximum biomass concentration of 0.71 g/l^{-1} and corresponding β -carotene content of 4.76% were obtained, β -carotene yield was 32.0 mg/l^{-1} [12]. According to Sui *et al.*, 2021, *D. salina* DF15 (CCAP 19/41 (PLY DF15)) produced more than 12% β -carotene (ash-free dry weight (AFDW) basis), and red light triggered the production of 9-*cis* β -carotene at a 9-*cis/all-trans* β -carotene ratio of 1.5 [13]. With key roles of carotenoid compounds, especially beta-carotene are high bioactive compositions in microalgae *Dunaliella salina*. Therefore, this study focuses on evaluation of total carotenoid and beta-carotene contents in the microalgae powder *D. salina* and *D. bardawil* cultivated in Vietnam.

Materials and Methods

Research subjects

Microalgae powder of *Dunaliella salina* CCAP 19/18 and *Dunaliella bardawil* DCCBC 15 were obtained from microalgal biomass cultivated in the Biochemistry and Toxicology Laboratory at Nguyen Tat Thanh University. The algal strains were cultured in MD4 medium containing 1.5M NaCl, with light intensity of 100 $\mu\text{mol/m}^2/\text{s}$, and cultivation temperature maintained at 25°C \pm 2°C. After 24 days of cultivation, biomass was harvested by centrifugation at 6,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 10°C, washed, and then dried to a constant weight. The microalgae powder was stored at -20°C.

Methods

Evaluation of microalgae powder

The obtained microalgae powder was ground using a porcelain mortar and pestle to achieve a fine, homogeneous consistency and was stored at -20°C. The *Dunaliella salina* and *Dunaliella bardawil* powders were

visually examined with the naked eye and observed under an optical microscope at 400X magnification to characterize the microalgae sample morphology.

Total carotenoid determination using UV-VIS method

Carotenoid extraction using hexane solvent: Weigh 0.5 g of algal powder into a capped test tube, add 5 mL hexane. Vortex and heat at 50°C for 30 minutes. The obtained hexane solution was centrifuged at 6000 rpm, 20°C for 5 minutes. Discard the pellet and collect the supernatant, then evaporate to dryness. The remaining algal powder in the test tube was continuously extracted with hexane until the hexane solution became transparent. The residues from each extraction were collected in a beaker with hexane and evaporated to dryness. Dissolve the residue in the beaker to a final volume of 5 mL with hexane [14].

The obtained solution was measured at 450 nm wavelength, with hexane as the blank solution. Total carotenoid content was determined using the formula [14]:

Carotenoid ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) = $A_{450} \times 25.2$ Where: A_{450} is the absorbance measured at 450 nm.

Beta-carotene determination by HPLC method

HPLC instrument: Shimadzu serial L214555, PDA detector. Chromatographic conditions [15]: Gradient elution program, column: C18 – 4.6 x 250 mm, GL Sciences, temperature: 30°C, wavelength: 476 nm, injection volume: 30 μL , mobile phase: Dichloromethane: Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:45:15), flow rate: 1 mL/minute.

Standard solution: Accurately weigh approximately 10 mg of standard beta-carotene into a 50 mL volumetric flask, dissolve in hexane, and fill to volume. Pipette 1 mL of this solution into a 20 mL volumetric flask, complete with mobile phase. Filter through a 0.45 μm membrane.

System suitability test: Inject the 0.01 mg/mL standard beta-carotene sample 6 times under the selected chromatographic conditions and record the chromatogram. Requirements: retention time, peak area, tail factor, and theoretical plate number all with RSD < 2%. Peak tail factor (Tf) < 2, theoretical plate number > 3000, indicating system compatibility.

Beta-carotene standard curve: Prepare concentrations from 2 to 14 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Start with a 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ initial solution, dilute to standard solutions of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Inject into the system under selected chromatographic conditions. Construct a linear regression equation and plot a correlation diagram between peak area and beta-carotene concentration.

Test solution: The residue obtained after extracting 0.5 g of algal powder with hexane, made up to 5 mL. Accurately pipette 1 mL of hexane extract into a 5 mL volumetric flask and complete with mobile phase. Filter through a 0.45 μm membrane. Inject the test sample into the system under selected chromatographic

conditions. Perform beta-carotene content determination 6 times for each algal sample. Beta-carotene content is calculated using the beta-carotene standard curve equation, where y is the peak area and x is the beta-carotene content (µg/mL).

Data Analysis

Data were processed using Microsoft office Excel 2016 and analyzed Paired - samples T test using SPSS 20.0 software with significance error $p < 0.05$

Results

Evaluation of microalgae powder

Visually, both microalgae powders were fine, homogeneous, non-agglomerated, with a slightly pungent odor. The *D. bardawil* powder (Figure 1b) displayed a more intense yellow color compared to the *D. salina* powder (Figure 1a).

Figure 1: The Microalgal Powder *Dunaliella salina* (a) and *Dunaliella bardawil* (b)

Figure 2: *Dunaliella salina* (a) and *Dunaliella bardawil* (b) Microalgae Powders under 400X Optical Microscopy

Under 400X optical microscopic observation, no significant morphological differences were detected between the two microalgae species. Both microalgae species exhibited intact cells with variable morphologies: egg-shaped, pear-shaped, spindle-

shaped, or elliptical, with flagella. Intracellular structures were dense, containing organelle granules with green or yellowish hues. *D. bardawil* cells (Figure 2b) were larger and displayed a more intense green coloration compared to *D. salina* (Figure 2a).

Total carotenoid determination Using UV-VIS method

Each microalgae powder underwent six replicate carotenoid content measurements. Hexane extracts were spectrophotometrically analyzed at 450 nm. Results revealed statistically significant differences in average carotenoid content between *D. salina* and *D. bardawil*, with *D. bardawil* demonstrating higher carotenoid levels: $3.306 > 1.454$ (mg/g) ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 3, Table 2).

Figure 3: Carotenoid Content of *D. salina* and *D. bardawil* Microalgae

Determination of beta-carotene content by HPLC method

System suitability determination: A standard beta-carotene solution (0.01 mg/mL) was injected six times into the chromatographic system under pre-selected conditions, and chromatograms were recorded. Results demonstrated exceptional system compatibility, with the following parameters: Retention time, peak area, tailing factor, theoretical plate number. All parameters exhibited relative standard deviation (RSD) $< 2\%$. Specifically: average peak tailing factor (Tf) = 1.216 (< 2), average theoretical plate number = 21,661 (> 3000). These metrics, illustrated in Figure 4 and Table 1, confirm the system's suitability and method's reliability for beta-carotene analysis.

Table 1: Table of Results for Determining System Compatibility

No.	Retention time (minute)	Peak area (mAU)	Tailing factor (Tf)	Theoretical Plate Number (N)
1	11.944	2006727	1.228	21724
2	11.937	1995718	1.234	21907
3	11.942	2008922	1.217	21594
4	11.940	1999499	1.207	22126
5	11.942	2026661	1.205	21524
6	11.944	2009732	1.207	21093

AVER	11.942	2007877	1.216	21661
SD	0.003	10739.892	0.012	354.003
RSD	0.022	0.535	1.008	1.634

Figure 4: Chromatogram of the Standard Beta-Carotene Sample at a Concentration of 0.01 mg/mL

Constructing the standard curve for beta-carotene concentration from 2 to 14 µg/mL: Beta-carotene standard solutions with concentrations of 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 14 µg/mL were used to develop a linear regression equation under the selected chromatographic conditions. The resulting linear regression equation is: $y = 224708x - 26631$, where: y represents the peak area, x represents the beta-carotene concentration (µg/mL). The correlation plot between peak area and beta-carotene concentration was constructed with an R^2 value of 0.9976 (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Beta-Carotene Standard Curve

Figure 6: Chromatogram of Beta-Carotene Standard Solutions with Concentrations from 2 to 14 µg/mL

Determination of beta-carotene content in *Dunaliella salina* and *Dunaliella bardawil* microalgae:

Beta-carotene content was determined for each microalgae species through six repeated measurements. Extraction was performed using hexane solvent, with sample preparation and injection into the chromatographic system under pre-selected conditions, followed by chromatogram recording. Beta-carotene content for each microalgae species was calculated using the standard curve equation $y = 224708x - 26631$, where y represents peak area and x represents beta-carotene concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$). Analysis revealed statistically significant differences in the average beta-carotene content between *D. salina* and *D. bardawil* microalgae. *D. bardawil* demonstrated a higher beta-carotene content compared to *D. salina*: $0.172 > 0.117$ (mg/g), ($p < 0.05$).

The raw material powders of both microalgae species exhibited distinct carotenoid and beta-carotene profiles and proportions (Table 2). *D. bardawil* demonstrated higher carotenoid and beta-carotene

concentrations compared to *D. salina*. However, the beta-carotene to total carotenoid ratio in *D. salina* was higher than in *D. bardawil* ($8.073\% > 5.213\%$), ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2).

Figure 7: Beta-Carotene Content of *Dunaliella Salina* and *Dunaliella Bardawil* Microalgae

Table 2: Carotenoid and Beta-Carotene Content in *Dunaliella salina* and *Dunaliella bardawil* Microalgae

	Total carotenoid content (mg/g)	Beta-caroten content (mg/g)	Beta-caroten/carotenoid ratio (%)
<i>D. salina</i>	1.454 ± 0.016	$0.117 \pm 0,020$	8.073 ± 0.223
<i>D. bardawil</i>	3.306 ± 0.061	0.172 ± 0.028	$5.213 \pm 0,145$

Discussion

These observations align with the known morphological characteristics of *Dunaliella* microalgae, where cell shape and size vary depending on environmental conditions, ranging from 5 to 25 μm in length and 3 to 13 μm in width. The cells possess flagella and lack a polysaccharide cell wall [16]. The microalgal powders have a yellow color and intact cells that represent accumulation of carotenoids and ensure their use in functional foods.

The *D. salina* and *D. bardawil* powders demonstrated high carotenoid content, with *D. bardawil* having a higher content compared to *D. salina*. Park *et al.*, 2013 compared the responses of two *Dunaliella* strains, *D. salina* CCAP 19/18 and *D. bardawil* to light intensity, the results showed that they are well known for carotenogenesis, the β -carotene content of *D. bardawil* was higher than that of *D. salina* CCAP 19/18 under all light intensities and the largest difference between the two strains occurred at $80 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (2.37 times difference) [17].

HPLC methods for beta-carotene analysis were reliable, with beta-carotene content significantly higher in *D. bardawil* compared to *D. salina*. The *Dunaliella* powders are known as natural carotenoid resources for human demand. These results align with previously

published research indicating the presence of multiple carotenoids in *Dunaliella* microalgae, including phytoene, zeaxanthin, lutein, and canthaxanthin [6]. Referencing prior studies, Lafarga (2016) highlighted variations in carotenoid production among different algal species, with beta-carotene to total carotenoid ratios potentially fluctuating based on environmental factors and cultivation conditions [18]. Sindhu's (2022) research further emphasized that the beta-carotene/total carotenoid ratio serves as a critical indicator of algae product quality, given beta-carotene's potent antioxidant properties and numerous potential applications [19].

Conclusion

The microalgae powders of *D. bardawil* and *D. salina* meet criteria for potential use as raw materials in commercial product manufacturing. *D. bardawil* demonstrated significantly higher carotenoid and beta-carotene content compared to *D. salina* ($p < 0.05$). The HPLC method, utilizing appropriate chromatographic conditions, reliably determined the beta-carotene concentration in the microalgae. The beta-carotene content in *D. bardawil* (1.723 mg/g) was substantially higher than in *D. salina* (1.174 mg/g). Both *D. bardawil* and *D. salina* microalgae powders exhibit promising potential as primary raw material sources for carotenoid and beta-carotene compound production,

with significant applications in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. These findings open opportunities for further research aimed at optimizing cultivation conditions to enhance carotenoid yields.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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